

CLASSIFICATION AND FUNCTIONS OF PROVERBS AND SAYINGS

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ANNOTATION: This article discusses the classification and functions of proverbs and sayings. It contains enough information about the role, importance and place of proverbs in speech. In addition, the linguistic character and influence of proverbs and sayings were also mentioned.

KEY WORDS: paremiological units, classification, genetic concept, expressions, phraseological units

In the modern world, in every language one can find such paremiological units as proverbs and sayings. They are used by native speakers in speech and writing: for example, in everyday communication with relatives and colleagues, in literary, musical and film works, on radio and television and on the Internet.

Proverbial sayings are used by both adults and children in order to warn or joke, to accurately characterize a person or his character, to give a colorful description of a life situation. The variety of proverbs and sayings is amazing: on any topic, you can pick up a significant number of sonorous expressions, be it love and friendship, family and marriage, work and rest, sadness and joy.

For convenient search and use, proverbs and sayings accumulated over the centuries must be classified. It is impossible not to appreciate the contribution of the outstanding Soviet folklorist G. L. Permyakov to the development of Russian paremiology. His paremiological theory won universal recognition and outlined the right path for the development of structural paremiology. In the works "Fundamentals of Structural Paremiology", the scientist notes that the classification of proverbs and sayings is the key issue of paremiology. In the course of the analysis of existing types of classification, it is possible to determine the most common in modern linguistics:

1) alphabetical classification. This is the most ancient and simple way of arranging proverbial expressions, based on the principle of placing in alphabetical order. For example, collections and publications by N. I. Tolstoy and I. V. Fedosov are based on it;

key word classification. This principle is based on the distribution of proverbs according to the key words that make up the figurative expression. The disadvantage of this classification is that one proverb can have several key words, thereby being listed in different semantic groups. According to the reference words, the contents of the works of A. M. Zhigulev, V. M. Mokienko and T. G. Nikitina are placed;

2) monographic classification is based on the combination of proverbs and sayings according to the place or time of their collection. This method is the most suitable in the event that historical interest comes to the fore. The negative aspects of the monographic classification include repetition and the lack of logical structuring of the material;

3) genetic classification distributes the material by origin. Particular attention is paid to the original language and the people who created it. The genetic concept intersects with the monographic one, repeating its shortcomings. According to this system, the dictionary of V. M. Mokienko was created;

4) thematic classification is based on the division of proverbs according to the topics of the utterance. This grouping system is the most frequent and used among paremiologists. A striking example is the work of V. I. Dahl, A. S. Spirin and V. I. Zimin. It should be noted that this classification is endowed with certain disadvantages. For example, some proverbs and sayings are characterized by multi-darkness, and cannot be attributed to one single section. Moreover, the compiler of the dictionary independently distributes paroemias by subject, therefore, his individual choice is not always guessed by the reader.

G. L. Permyakov is convinced that each system has both positive and negative sides, but none of them is based on the nature of proverbial sayings. According to the researcher, in order to correctly determine the nature of proverbs and sayings, it is necessary to consider them as a phenomenon of language, a phenomenon of thought and a phenomenon of folklore. Firstly, he offers his own interpretation of proverbs and sayings in order to differentiate them from other phraseological units. So, a proverb is a complete sentence with a permanent set of members, and a saying, due to its openness, is constantly replenished from the speech context. Secondly, the folklorist came to the conclusion about the symbolic nature of proverbs and sayings. He managed to establish that proverbial proverbs are signs of specific situations and relationships between things. That is why L. G. Permyakov came to the decision to make a classification of the situations themselves.

In the chapter "On the question of the structure of the paremiological fund", the author argues that the true theme of a proverb or saying lies in the opposition of two entities that form the basis of the meaning of the proverb, and by no means a reference to a specific word or field of activity to which the proverbial-saying expression can be attributed. This type of classification was called logical-semiotic, and pairs of phrases were called invariant thematic pairs. Among such pairs, there are "Good - Bad", "Rich - Poor", "Full - Hungry", "Much - Little" and many others. For example, the theme of the proverb "Grandfathers did not know trouble, but grandchildren gained torment" is not a family, not trouble, etc., but the invariant pair "Past - Future". Further, the author concentrates on a complete list of invariant pairs, clearly distinguishing each of them. For example, "Beginning - End" - about the beginning and end of things, about birth and death, about the beginning and end of the season, day: an English proverb says "Everything revolves around bread and death". "Strong - Weak" - about strong and weak things, as well as about influential and insignificant people: according to the French proverb "Parler est bien, mais faire est encore mieux". "Available - Inaccessible" - about things that are easy or, on the contrary, difficult to get: "A poor guy went bankrupt: he bought a copper ring for a girl."

Before studying the question of the functions that proverbs and sayings implement, one should determine their place in the language system. The linguist and paremiologist O. S. Anisimova studied in detail four approaches regarding the belonging of proverbial expressions to the language-speech system in her article "The Place of Proverbs in the Language-Speech System". The researcher identifies the following groups:

- 1) proverbs of the supralinguistic semiotic tier;
- 2) proverbs of the paremiological level;

- 3) proverbs as communicative phraseological units;
- 4) proverbs as units of language and units of speech.

Then the author focuses on each of the approaches, citing as an example linguists who adhere to one or another point of view. So, M. A. Cherkassky argued that due to the discrepancy between the plan of expression and the plan of content, proverbs are included in the supralinguistic semiotic tier. Paremiologist G. L. Permyakov attributed proverbs to the paremiological level of the language, which stands above all other levels. Finally, O. S. Anisimova shares the point of view of A. G. Grigoryan and G. D. Sidorkova on the belonging of proverbs to the language-speech system. Their hypothesis is explained by the fact that proverbial proverbs manifest themselves as language units - phraseological units, as well as speech units - texts, thereby combining their functions.

In order to prove the hypothesis, O. S. Anisimova analyzes the functions of language and speech and checks their implementation in proverbs. The researcher distinguishes from language functions: social, communicative, cognitive, cultural; from speech - nominative, emotive-voluntative, signal and ethnic. As examples illustrating the implementation of functions in proverbs, we selected proverbs from various collections and thesauri of the Russian, English and French languages.

As examples illustrating the implementation of functions in proverbs, we selected proverbs from various collections of Russian, English and French by such compilers as V. I. Kogut, S. S. Kuzmin, Gregory Titelman, V. S. Modestov and V. M. Mokienko.

O. S. Anisimova notes that the most significant is the cognitive, or epistemological, function, thanks to which proverbs help a person to cognize the surrounding reality.

"On connaît l'ami dans le besoin". - "Friend is known in trouble".

Further, the communicative function is highlighted, which is associated with the main goal of the proverb - to have the necessary impact on a person through the use of objective information, centuries-old experience and accumulated wisdom.

Don't count your chickens before they hatch. - "Do not count your chickens before they are hatched".

Performing a communicative function and influencing people's behavior, proverbs also realize a social function that allows you to organize society and enlighten the people.

"Repos est demi-vie". - "To live without work is only to smoke the sky."

The last function that proverbs perform is a cultural function, which can be explained by the fact that each proverb is a reflection of the specific characteristics of the people, their mentality, beliefs and way of life. Proverbs contain many years of experience and wisdom of people, transmitted through the years.

"God helps those who help themselves." "Trust in God, but don't make a mistake yourself".

Let us illustrate four speech functions implemented in proverbial proverbs, which are distinguished by O. S. Anisimova:

- 1) nominative - allows you to set the object of thought in the proverb ("The apple never falls far from the tree." - "The apple does not fall far from the apple tree");
- 2) emotive-volitional - responsible for the manifestation of human feelings and emotions ("Chose promise, chose due." - "Promised - do it!");
- 3) signal - encourages to perform an action or, conversely, warns ("Dans le doute, abstiens-toi!" - "If in doubt, refrain!");

4) ethnic - conveys information about the cultural and ethnic characteristics of the interlocutor ("What is great for a Russian, then death for a German").

Linguist-paremiologist O. S. Anisimova emphasizes the insignificant informativeness of proverbs due to their wide and frequent use. The researcher, however, is sure that the lack of informativeness is compensated by a number of pragmatic functions carried out in proverbial expressions. These pragmatic functions are described in detail in the research work by I. Yu. Moiseeva and E. V. Chudina "Pragmatic functions of proverbs and sayings". Linguists pay attention to three pragmatic functions of proverbs and sayings as "pragmatically charged" statements.

1) Accentuation of attention: the use of figurative expressions of an instructive nature against the background of neutral vocabulary allows the speaker to enhance the speech impact.

2) Identification of speech elements necessary for the communication process: there is a correlation with the function of accentuation of attention, since the main characteristics of proverbial proverbs come to the fore.

3) Compression of information: due to their conciseness and metaphorical nature, proverbs and sayings allow in a short form to convey to the addressee a correctly formulated idea.

Summarizing the above, we can conclude that proverbs and sayings belong to the language-speech system, since they implement language and speech functions. In order to classify a great variety of proverbial proverbs, there are various types of grouping used by different linguists-paremiologists in their works. It is impossible not to mention the contribution of the Soviet scientist G. L. Permyakov, whose classification according to invariant thematic pairs is of particular importance in domestic and foreign scientific circles.

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